

STRESS, ANXIETY, AND DEPRESSION AMONG PARENTS IN CEBU

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ABSTRACT

Stress, anxiety, and depression can affect anyone and manifest through mental, emotional, physical, behavioral, or physiological symptoms. There are instances where the manifestations may worsen the levels of the conditions. Current research focuses mostly on parents' experiences in relation to having children with certain needs, illnesses, or as aftereffects of the COVID-19 pandemic. This study focuses on stress, anxiety, and depression among parents of enrolled students from two universities, labeled as HEI 1 and HEI 2, with a total number of 697 participants. Researcher-made instruments were produced that had a 4-point Likert scale for measurement, with stress and depression having 37 statements and anxiety having 36 statements. All statements focused on the different levels of the three, namely none, low, moderate, and high; and the manifestations they observed in themselves within the past two weeks (fourteen days) upon answering. All results from both universities were tallied as one large population to find the frequency and percentage per statement and points in the scale. Based on the collected data, the participants experienced manifestations at different levels. The majority showed no signs of stress, anxiety, or depression. However, there were parents who reported low to high levels of the three conditions, which were manifested cognitively, emotionally, behaviorally, and physiologically. There were manifestations that were common across the different levels, indicating that despite the level of condition they were in, they still experienced them.

Keywords: *stress, anxiety, depression, parents, Cebu*

INTRODUCTION

Hans Selye coined stress in 1956. He defined it as the non-specific response of the body to a demand, which entails that it is a reaction to the body's response to any change, threat, or pressure put upon it, from outside forces or from within, that may eventually protect the body from potential harm. The American Psychological Association (APA) (2018) describes stress as a normal reaction to everyday pressures that can become unhealthy when it upsets a person's day-to-day functioning. The World Health Organization (WHO, 2023) also defines stress as a state of worry or mental tension caused by a problematic situation. Lovin et al. (2022) found that stress has a detrimental influence, leading to frustration and increased difficulty in managing situations. In today's environment, stress has become a worldwide phenomenon that manifests itself in a variety of ways.

Parents in today's generation are generally working longer hours, as increased levels of responsibility demand them to strain themselves even more rigorously to fulfill rising performance standards. Parental stress occurs when a parent's perceptions of the demands of parenting outweigh their ability to deal with them (Leitch et al., 2019). While all experience stress from time to time, prolonged or chronic stress can have a negative impact on one's mental health, impair daily functioning, and emotional equilibrium. When it becomes chronic, it increases the chances of developing anxiety and depression (Agyapong et al., 2022)

The National Institute of Mental Health (2015) stresses out that anxiety is one's body's response to stress, and it can occur even when there is no immediate threat. This is characterized by a chronic and excessive sense of tense, fear, or unease about future events or situations, which is frequently accompanied by physical and emotional symptoms. Individuals suffering with anxiety may find it difficult to manage their worrisome thoughts, which can lead to a sense of being overwhelmed and out of control.

Parents may feel stressed out and anxious for a variety of reasons, as the role of parent comes with a plethora of obstacles and duties. The magnitude of parenting obligations can be overwhelming. As can be observed, raising and nurturing a child requires a constant juggling act of work, housework, and childcare, leaving parents with little time for themselves. Financial challenges add to the stress, as providing for a family and maintaining a stable environment necessitates significant resources. Furthermore, parents frequently make personal sacrifices by putting their own needs and interests on hold to prioritize their children's welfare. This selflessness can result in feelings of anger, resentment, or loss of identity, which can contribute to mental health issues like depression.

Depression is a major mental illness that has a significant impact on an individual's quality of life. Although the etiologies of this condition are unknown, growing attention has been focused on the influence of psychological stress on depression (Yang et al., 2015).

Given the unique challenges of the parenting role, marked by emotional highs and lows, parents are particularly susceptible to mental health issues. This

underscores the necessity of conducting research into the stress, anxiety, and depression experienced by parents, to thoroughly comprehend the nuances of parental mental health, identify effective support mechanisms, and ultimately improve the well-being of both parents and their children.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the stress, anxiety, and depression of parents in Cebu through answering the following questions:

1. What are the levels of stress, anxiety, and depression of parents?
2. What are the common manifestations of stress of parents in terms of:
 - 2.1. cognitive,
 - 2.2. emotional,
 - 2.3. behavioral, and
 - 2.4. physiological?
3. What are the common manifestations of anxiety in parents in terms of:
 - 3.1. cognitive,
 - 3.2. emotional,
 - 3.3. behavioral, and
 - 3.4. physiological?
4. What are the common manifestations of depression in parents in terms of:
 - 4.1. cognitive,
 - 4.2. emotional, and
 - 4.3. behavioral?
5. Is there a significant relationship between:
 - 5.1. stress and anxiety?
 - 5.2. stress and depression? and
 - 5.3. anxiety and depression?

METHODOLOGY

Participants

The participants of this study were the parents of the enrolled students in HEI 1 and HEI 2. It was conducted on the day the respective institutions held a parents' workshop on mental health. The workshop was facilitated by a Registered Psychologist and was assisted by guidance counselors, principals, teachers, psychometricians, and psychology interns.

Instrument

The researcher curated her own questionnaire that contained statements showing common manifestations or effects of stress, anxiety, and depression. Each variable had its own questionnaire, with stress and depression having thirty-seven (37) statements and anxiety having thirty-six (36). It also used a 4-point Likert scale, using 0–4, for its measurement.

Procedure

The researcher prepared questionnaires to identify the level of stress, anxiety, and depression of the research participants. An informed consent form was stated at the bottom page of each instrument for the research participants to sign should they agree to participate in the research conducted. An appointment was set with the guidance counselors of the first institution where the study was conducted, to be referred as HEI 1, and with the principals of elementary and junior high school departments of the second institution labeled as HEI 2. The questionnaires were given to each department for review and reproduction.

Before the start of the workshop, a one-hour ushering-in activity was done, where participants were given the instruments and instructions. Guidance counselors, teachers, and psychology interns were strategically situated in the venue to assist at least 5-7 parents, making sure that someone would answer their questions or clarifications. Once the questionnaires were given to them, the consent forms were cut off and gathered, but they were placed separately to further keep the answers random and confidential.

All the questionnaires were then collated into one population. Each statement of every variable and its corresponding answers were then tallied to produce their frequency and percentage in the population. The researcher then clustered the statements into tables that showed similarities in nature and labeled it with its respective theme.

Statistical Treatment

The data gathered was used to check the levels of stress, anxiety, and depression in parents. In order to interpret it correctly, descriptive statistics was used. The percentage was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Percentage \%} = \frac{f}{N} \times 100\%$$

Where:

% = Percentage

f = Frequency

N = Total number of participants

Furthermore, relationships between the Stress, Anxiety and Depression level of parents were obtained using the Chi-Square test of Independence. Chi square value χ^2 is computed as:

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(f_o - f_E)^2}{f_E}$$

Where:

f_o = observed frequency

f_E = expected frequency

RESULTS

This section presents the tabulated format of the gathered data from the three variables: stress, anxiety, and depression. The first table in every area shows the collected answers with its percentage for the four different levels: none, low, moderate, and high. The results of this study were then grouped according to the variable to which the statement was assigned. There were some statements that were clustered into groups as they showed a similar nature, such as their effects or type of manifestation. They were tabulated with the corresponding statement and per point in the scale, showing their frequency and percentage.

The statements presented in the table are those that were included in the top three most common manifestations for those who experienced low, moderate, and high levels of the variables. It was further filtered by only showcasing the statement(s) that were present in all three levels. However, due to the emotional manifestations of stress having no shared statements between the three levels, the three most common answers for each level are presented.

At the end of the last variable, the contingency tables that follow show the correlation between the three variables. The testing of its significance was also done and explained.

Stress

Table 1. Level of Stress

LEVEL OF STRESS	Observed	Percentage
NO STRESS	350	53%
LOW STRESS	216	32.7%
MODERATE STRESS	54	8.2%
HIGH STRESS	41	6.2%

The tabulated result shows that among the parents, the majority, constituting 53%, reported experiencing no stress, while 32.7% indicated low levels of stress. This suggests that a significant portion of parents perceive their stress levels as manageable or minimal. However, it's crucial to acknowledge the smaller yet still significant percentages reporting moderate (8.2%) and high (6.2%) levels of stress.

Table 2. *Cognitive Manifestations of Stress*

Statements	No		Low		Moderate		High	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
My income is not enough to buy the things my family and I need.	240	34.43	240	34.43	103	14.78	108	15.49

The most common manifestation that was evident in the low, moderate, and high levels was the statement, “*My income is not enough to buy the things my family and I need.*” It garnered 240 (34.43%), 103 (14.78%), and 108 (15.49%) answers, respectively. It ranked third in both the low and moderate levels of stress, while it ranked first in the high levels of stress.

Table 3. *Emotional Manifestations of Stress*

Statements	No		Low		Moderate		High	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
I feel that I have too much responsibility.	245	35.15	250	35.87			89	12.77
I feel that there are too many people I need to satisfy.	307	44.05			107	15.35		
I feel that people have high expectations of me.	264	37.88			116	16.64	78	11.19
I do not have enough time for leisure or my personal needs.	266	38.16	262	37.59	105	15.06		
I easily get irritated over small matters.	306	43.90	241	34.58				

I feel exhausted when deadlines are piled up	267	38.31			105	15.06		
I feel like crying when responsibilities are too heavy to bear	303	43.47					79	11.33

Stress can have a significant impact on a parent's mental health, resulting in a number of apparent changes in mood. This explains the results presented in Table 3. There were a large number who never considered the manifestations stated above to be emotionally stressful, however there were still those who did.

For those who experienced low levels of stress, the three common manifestation of stress are *"I do not have enough time for leisure or my personal needs"* (f = 262; 37.59%), *"I feel that I have too much responsibility"* (f = 250; 35.87%), and *"I easily get irritated over small matters"* (f = 241; 34.58%). In the moderate level, they saw the expectations placed on them as the top stressor of the majority who answered such, with an f = 116 (16.64%), with *"I feel that there are too many people I need to satisfy"* (f = 107; 15.35%) and *"I do not have enough time for leisure or my personal needs"* (f = 105; 15.06%) following it. To those who answered high levels of stress, the top three common manifestations were *"I feel that I have too much responsibility"* (f= 89; 12.77%), *"I feel that people have high expectations of me"* (f= 78; 11.19%), and *"I feel like crying when responsibilities are too heavy to bear"* (f = 79; 11.33%).

Table 4. Behavioral Manifestations of Stress

Statements	No		Low		Moderate		High	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%

Statements	No		Low		Moderate		High	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
I am irritated around messy/disorganized environment.	201	28.84	264	37.88	114	16.36	110	15.78
I am easily irritated with loud noise.	253	36.30	251	36.01	114	16.36	66	9.47

Among the different statements, *"I am irritated around a messy/disorganized environment"* and *"I am easily irritated with loud noise"* were found to be among the top three most common answers in all three levels.

The statement *"I am irritated around a messy/disorganized environment"* ranked second for those with low levels of stress, with a frequency of 264 (37.88%).

For those with moderate and high levels of stress, it ranked first, having 114 (16.36%) and 110 (15.78%) answers, respectively. For the statement “*I am easily irritated with loud noise*”, it placed third for both low (f = 251; 36.01%) and high (f = 66; 9.47%) levels of stress, while also taking the first rank for moderate levels of stress. It garnered 114 (16.36%) answers as well.

Table 5. *Physiological Manifestations of Stress*

Statements	No		Low		Moderate		High	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
I experience cold flashes/sweating/increased heart rate when questioned about unfinished tasks.	357	51.22	206	29.65	80	11.48	44	6.31
When tasks are piled up, I can feel my head aches.	253	36.30	275	39.45	89	12.77	65	9.33

In table 5, there were a number of parents who felt no levels of physiological stress, but there were still those who felt low to high levels of it. The parents who answered low, moderate, and high levels of stress all found headaches to be a common manifestation garnering answers of 275 (39.45%) for low levels, 89 (12.77%) moderate levels, and 65 (9.33%) for high levels. Additionally, other physiological changes such as cold flashes/sweating/increased heart rate when asked about their unfinished tasks were evident; low levels had a number of 206 (29.65%), moderate levels had 80 (11.48%), and high levels had 44 (6.31%).

ANXIETY

Table 6. Levels of Anxiety

LEVEL OF ANXIETY	Observed	Percentage
NO ANXIETY	395	59.8%
LOW ANXIETY	195	29.5%
MODERATE ANXIETY	50	7.6%
HIGH ANXIETY	21	3.2%

The tabulated results provide insight into the levels of anxiety experienced by the parents. It's encouraging to note that a significant majority, comprising 59.8% of respondents, reported experiencing no anxiety. Additionally, 29.5% indicated low

levels of anxiety. This suggests that a substantial portion of parents perceive their anxiety levels as manageable or minimal, which could reflect a generally positive mental well-being. However, it's essential to address the smaller yet notable percentages reporting moderate (7.6%) and high (3.2%) levels of anxiety.

Table 7. *Cognitive Manifestations of Anxiety*

Statements	No		Low		Moderate		High	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Cannot put disappointments out of my mind	259	37.16	205	29.41	74	10.62	39	5.60
Cannot stop overthinking	221	31.71	230	33.00	74	10.62	60	8.61

In table 7, there were those who felt no levels of anxiety, but those who answered low to high levels should be noted. For the parents who felt low, moderate, and high levels of anxiety, they all answered on their inability to stop overthinking, as the most common reason why they experienced such levels, which collected 230 (33%), 74 (10.62%), and 60 (8.61%) answers, respectively. There was also a tie between the statements “cannot stop overthinking” and “cannot put disappointments out of my mind” for those who answered moderate levels of anxiety. The statement “cannot put disappointments out of my mind” also placed third for low level (f = 205; 29.41%) and second for high levels (f = 39; 5.60%).

Table 8. *Emotional Manifestations of Anxiety*

Statements	No		Low		Moderate		High	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Feeling constantly worried and afraid about what might happen	263	37.73	212	30.42	68	9.76	42	6.03

In Table 8, it shows that there were parents who felt no levels of anxiety at all. For those who experienced low and moderate levels, the statement “feeling constantly worried and afraid about what might happen” was a common emotional reaction, garnering 212 (30.42%) and 68 (9.76%) answers, respectively, and it being the second most common for the high level with 42 answers (6.03%).

Table 9. Behavioral Manifestations of Anxiety

Statements	No		Low		Moderate		High	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Easily annoyed or irritated	244	35.01	226	32.42	76	10.90	34	4.88

The statement “*easily annoyed or irritated*” ranked the highest for low levels (f = 226; 32.42%) and moderate levels (f = 76; 10.90%) and second for high levels (f = 34; 4.88%). This statement was seen in all three levels since parents' irritability is apparently a common manifestation.

Table 10. Physiological Manifestations of Anxiety

Statements	No		Low		Moderate		High	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Experienced hot and/or cold sweats	325	46.63	181	25.97	59	8.46	19	2.73

Table 10 presents the parents' physiological manifestations of anxiety. There were those who experienced none of them since they felt no levels of anxiety, while the others felt different levels and experienced different manifestations or effects. It was the statement “*experienced hot and/or cold sweats*” that was present in all three levels as it ranked second for low (f = 181; 25.97%), first for moderate (f = 59; 8.46%), and third for high (f = 19; 2.73%) levels.

DEPRESSION

Table 11. Levels of Depression

LEVEL OF DEPRESSION	Observed	Percentage
NO DEPRESSION	462	69.9%
LOW DEPRESSION	145	21.9%
MODERATE DEPRESSION	34	5.1%
HIGH DEPRESSION	20	3%

The tabulated result presents the levels of depression experienced by parents. It's reassuring to see that the vast majority, accounting for 69.9% of the participants,

reported experiencing no depression, while 21.9% indicated low levels of depression. These findings suggest that a significant portion of parents perceive their mental well-being to be relatively stable. However, it is important to note the smaller percentages reporting moderate (5.1%) and high (3%) levels of depression.

Table 12. *Cognitive Manifestations of Depression*

Statements	No		Low		Moderate		High	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Negative thoughts kept haunting me especially when I'm alone or at night.	369	52.94	217	31.13	58	8.32	42	6.03

The table reveals that while a significant portion of parents, presented in Table 11, showed no signs of depression, there were individuals experiencing varying levels of it—low, moderate, and high. Specifically, the statement “Negative thoughts kept haunting me especially when I’m alone or at night” consistently ranked among the top manifestations across all three levels: second in the low levels (f = 217; 31.13%), third in moderate (f = 58; 8.32%), and first in high levels (f = 42; 6.03%).

Table 13. *Emotional Manifestations of Depression*

Statements	No		Low		Moderate		High	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
I feel disappointed of my past actions.	284	40.75	261	37.45	77	11.05	64	9.18
I am sensitive to other people’s comments about me.	349	50.07	216	30.99	74	10.62	43	6.17

There are two statements that are common in the three levels of depression. The first was “*I feel disappointed by my past actions*”, which ranked first in all levels having 261 (37.45%), 77 (11.05%), and 64 (9.18%) answers, respectively. The next statement was “*I am sensitive to other people’s comments about me*”. It ranked second in the low (f = 216; 30.99%) and moderate (f = 74; 10.62%) levels, while it ranked third for the high levels (f = 43; 6.17%).

Table 14. Behavioral Manifestations of Depression

Statements	No		Low		Moderate		High	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
I feel tired most of the time.	297	42.61	252	36.15	73	10.47	60	8.61
I have days when I don't have the energy to get up from bed.	262	37.59	296	42.47	90	12.91	39	5.60

There were those who felt no level of depression, thus not showing any of the manifestations. For those who felt low, moderate, and high depression levels, they all had statements “*I feel tired most of the time*” and “*I have days when I don't have the energy to get up from bed*” among their top ranked answers.

The statement “*I feel tired most of the time*” was third in the low (f = 252; 36.15%) level, second in moderate (f = 73; 10.47%), and first with 60 answers (8.61%) in the high level. The statement “*I have days when I don't have the energy to get up from bed*” was the highest for both low and moderate levels, with 296 (42.47%) and 90 (12.91%) responses accordingly, while it ranked third for high levels with 39 (5.60%) answers.

Correlation

Table 15. Contingency Table for the Relationship of Stress and Anxiety Levels

LEVEL OF STRESS	LEVEL OF ANXIETY				TOTAL
	NO ANXIETY	LOW ANXIETY	MODERATE ANXIETY	HIGH ANXIETY	
NO STRESS	318	24	6	2	350
LOW STRESS	61	144	10	1	216
MODERATE STRESS	5	24	22	3	54
HIGH STRESS	11	3	12	15	41
TOTAL	395	195	50	21	661

The contingency table illustrates a significant relationship between the stress and anxiety levels of parents, as indicated by the p-value of less than 0.001. Notably, the data highlights varying patterns of stress and anxiety experiences among parents. Among parents experiencing high stress, 36.6% also reported high anxiety levels, while only 26.7% of parents with low stress reported high anxiety. Similarly, there's a notable difference in the distribution of anxiety levels among parents with different

stress levels. This suggests that higher stress levels may correspond to higher anxiety levels among parents.

Table 16. Contingency Table for the Relationship of Stress and Depression Levels

LEVEL OF STRESS	LEVEL OF DEPRESSION				TOTAL
	NO DEPRESSION	LOW DEPRESSION	MODERATE DEPRESSION	HIGH DEPRESSION	
NO STRESS	330	16	2	2	350
LOW STRESS	104	103	8	1	216
MODERATE STRESS	15	23	13	3	54
HIGH STRESS	13	3	11	14	41
TOTAL	462	145	34	20	661

Table 16 shows a significant relationship between the levels of stress and depression of parents supported by a p-value of less than 0.001. The data illustrates varying patterns of depression levels across different stress categories among parents. Among parents experiencing high stress, 34.1% reported high depression levels, compared to only 0.5% of parents with low stress. Similarly, there's a noticeable difference in the distribution of depression levels among parents with different stress levels. This suggests a strong association between stress and depression among parents, where higher stress levels correspond to higher levels of depression, and vice versa.

Table 17. Contingency Table for the Relationship of Anxiety and Depression Levels

LEVEL OF ANXIETY	LEVEL OF DEPRESSION				TOTAL
	NO DEPRESSION	LOW DEPRESSION	MODERATE DEPRESSION	HIGH DEPRESSION	
NO ANXIETY	372	21	0	2	395
LOW ANXIETY	77	106	10	2	195
MODERATE ANXIETY	9	17	21	3	50
HIGH ANXIETY	4	1	3	13	21
TOTAL	462	145	34	20	661

The contingency table provided indicates a significant relationship between the anxiety and depression levels of parents, supported by a p-value of less than 0.001. The data illustrates varying patterns of depression levels across different anxiety categories among parents. Among parents experiencing high anxiety, 61.9% reported high depression levels, compared to only 0.5% of parents with low anxiety. Similarly, there's a noticeable difference in the distribution of depression levels among parents with different anxiety levels.

DISCUSSION

This section discussed the implications of the results and their consistency with other literature.

The first table showed the observed data and its percentage for each level of stress. Its findings underscore the diverse experiences of stress among parents and emphasize the importance of prioritizing mental well-being within the family unit. It was then furthered into four different aspects of manifestation, namely cognitive, emotional, behavioral, and physiological.

The cognitive manifestations of stress were presented in Table 2. Only one statement was evidently among the top pressing issues for the parents, which often left them thinking and then led to feeling stressed. It was the statement, "*My income is not enough to buy the things my family and I need.*" This coincides with Mylenko's (2015) statement that financial reasons are a common reason for stress. The study of Islam et al. (2020) showed similar results, discussing that adults find economic hardships a mental stressor. The result also shows that even the slightest level of stress may present cognitive manifestations, but it was their financial status or struggles that became a burden that most of the participants found to be a common factor.

The results presented in Table 3 coincide with current literature. In this study, it was seen in those who felt low and moderate stress that their leisure time was affected, which is a similar finding to Siregar et al. (2021), who saw links between stress and the negative change in an individual's private life. With the participants being parents, it is expected that they have expectations and responsibilities to manage. As seen with the statement "*I feel that I have too much responsibility*" in the low and high levels, the statement "*I feel that people have high expectations of me*" in the moderate and high levels, and the statement "*I feel that there are too many people I need to satisfy*" in the moderate level, which may relate to the result on their roles to portray. There were also parents who scored in the low level who felt "*I easily get irritated over small matters*" while others scored high levels for the statement "*I feel like crying when responsibilities are too heavy to bear.*" These findings are in consonance with the findings of Attia et al (2022) that if one is stressed out, one can also observe a rise in anger, mood fluctuations, agitation, irritability, loneliness, or anxious or depressed expressions. Stanborough's (2020) article also supports that crying, or even just the feeling of wanting to cry, may serve as a signal of distress.

When it comes to behaviors, stress can have a negative effect on these in noticeable ways. These behaviors are not seen in the parents who showed no levels of stress in Table 4 but may be evident in different ways for parents who felt low to high levels of stress. With the parents in the study, they found themselves to be more irritable when seeing a messy environment or with loud noises. This result coincided with the result of a study that found a significant relationship between stress and noise (Jensen et al., 2019). Bhui et al. 's (2016) findings also presented that working adults rather have themselves organized because seeing a messy work environment would make them worry and stressed. This suggests that the participants who reported feeling low to high levels of stress may have been going through these behavioral changes in which their reaction to their visual and auditory stressors became prevalent in all three levels, possibly impacting on their everyday performance.

In Table 5, the statement "*I experience cold flashes/ sweating/ increased heart rate when questioned about unfinished tasks*" suggests that tasks and obligations are a reason for stress, which can worsen when unfinished. The physiological manifestation of it, which is sweating, is supported by the study of Zamkah et al. (2020) who found that sweating is a part of the body's stress detection system. For the statement "*When tasks are piled up, I can feel my head aches*" being among the most common coincides with the findings that adults would experience aches, pains, and muscle strains. The presence of frequent headaches or migraines is also possible (Guevarra & Cimanés, 2017).

Looking at the results presented in Tables 2-5, despite going through different levels of stress, the parents manifest common symptoms or share the same triggers and stressors. The research findings highlight various cognitive, emotional, behavioral, and physiological symptoms of stress among parents. Financial concerns emerged as a predominant cognitive stressor across all levels, reflecting the burden of economic hardships on mental well-being. Emotional manifestations varied, with low stress levels associated with time constraints and feelings of excessive responsibility, while moderate and high levels were characterized by societal expectations and overwhelming responsibilities, often leading to emotional distress such as irritability and crying. Behavioral changes included heightened irritability in chaotic environments and sensitivity to loud noise, indicating potential disruptions in daily functioning. Physiological symptoms, such as headaches and physical discomfort related to unfinished tasks, were reported across all stress levels, suggesting a tangible impact on physical health. These findings underscore the multifaceted nature of stress and its pervasive effects on various aspects of parental well-being.

Similar to the first table, Table 6 presents the different levels that the parents of the study felt, but this time their anxiety levels. Further manifestations were then seen in the parents through their cognitive, emotional, behavioral, and physiological aspects. The first listed item was seen in Table 7. With the anxiety associated with having children, some people may believe that their disappointments are directed at themselves due to how they performed their roles or what transpired with their child (Gershoff et al., 2010). Hence, they manifest these cognitive symptoms of anxiety, in the statements "*cannot put disappointments out of my mind*" and "*cannot stop overthinking.*" However, it is also possible that those participants who feel no anxiety may still experience worrying and overthinking, as it is a normal occurrence in life

(National Institute of Mental Health, 2022). The main distinction, along with the other manifestations or triggers, is that it had no impact on how well they performed as parents in their day-to-day activities.

Such results were possible in Table 8 as parents' mental health can be significantly impacted by anxiety, which can result in a variety of apparent changes in their feelings. As one goes through bouts of anxiety and its symptoms, it heightens their worries and fears; hence, significantly impacting on their feeling and levels of anxiety (National Institute of Mental Health, 2022). For participants who felt such levels of anxiety, most likely they have also impaired their emotional-regulation and heightened negative emotions thus, experienced apparent changes in their feelings. Although, the results do not necessarily mean that those who reported no anxiety did not experience feelings of heightened worries. It can be inferred that they do not dwell on these emotions for too long, keeping their anxiety levels from rising.

As parents navigate their own demands and challenges, their anxiety may be manifested in their actions, as stated in Table 9. Although anxiety-related behavioral manifestations can vary widely from person to person, they are always accompanied by observable adjustments in behavior and perspective on situations. This rings true for the parents of the study, as there were those who experienced no levels of anxiety; and thus, did not manifest any of them; while there were those who felt low to high levels of anxiety. It was even found in other literature, with Savage et al. (2015) explaining that it can also be triggered by either genetic or environmental factors. Based on the results, it is evident that the parents' most common behavioral manifestation is irritability. However, those participants who scored no anxiety may still have displayed these behavioral changes, but they may have successfully regulated these behaviors or may not have connected these actions to anxiety.

The results in Table 10 are explained and supported in the study of Asmundson and Katz (2009), as they saw that anxiety levels may cause hormones to activate the sweat glands. Moreover, as the body tries to regulate its temperature, it frequently sweats, notably on the palms or underarms. Their finding and Folk's (2021) statement about body temperature fluctuating in times of anxiety support the results found.

In summary for the anxiety-related manifestations, the results presented in tables 7-10 show that parents often overthink and focus on the negative side of their experiences, thus making them weary and afraid, having to constantly worry about what could possibly happen. They fear that the worst may be the outcome of their situation which might make them a burden to others. These add to their anxiety levels and would lead them to being short-tempered or easily irritated, resulting in them to also experience sweating and palpitations.

As to the variable on depression, Table 11 presents the levels of the parents who answered the survey. It was Table 12 that showed the cognitive manifestations of it. The findings indicate that individuals experiencing depression tend to focus on negative experiences and struggle to see any positive qualities in themselves. This aligns with Berry's (2022) research, which suggests that negative self-perceptions are a common characteristic of depression, evident in the top-ranking statements across all three levels of depression. Such negative thought patterns, whether dwelling on

past events or anticipating future ones, can intensify depressive symptoms or contribute to the onset of depression (American Psychiatric Association, n.d.).

As parents go through their everyday struggles and activities, they may encounter triggers that may result in them feeling different levels of depression. For those who participated in the study, there were those who reported experiencing none of the emotional manifestations while there were those who reported feeling low to high depression levels in Table 13. The finding that *"I feel disappointed of my past actions"* ranked first across all levels of depression aligns with existing literature, which suggests that experiencing repeated disappointments or dwelling on them can contribute to depressive feelings (Gold & Kadriu, 2019; Sandage et al., 2017; Skodol et al., 2015). Pincus et al. (2014) also found that disappointments exacerbate depression levels and raise the risk of developing it further. The statement *"I am sensitive to other people's comments about me"*, which is also a common manifestation in all three levels, can be supported by Grahek et al.'s (2019) finding that depression is found to be related to the impairment of cognitive and emotional processes. As a result, they may become more sensitive to the comments and opinions of others as they cannot process their emotions, and such comments may add to the negativity they are already feeling.

A variety of observable actions and routines are included in the behavioral manifestations of depression which some of those were present in the parents who participated in the study. Table 14 presents the behavioral manifestations associated with depression among participating parents. While some parents did not exhibit any signs of depression, others did, experiencing varying levels of it. Notably, regardless of the severity of depression, common behavioral indicators included frequently feeling tired and experiencing days where individuals lacked the energy to get out of bed. This relates to the findings of Corfield et al. (2016), who saw that people who are sad or exhibit this symptom are more likely to feel worn out, and to Fletcher's (2022), who saw the inability to get out of bed as being linked to fatigue and depression.

The manifestations of depression in parents presented in Tables 9–11 include constantly having negative thoughts, especially at night or when alone, though this still needs further study, especially the connection between depression and darkness. The manifestations of depression in this study are brought about by the negative thoughts that were connected to their self-perception and disappointments with their past actions. Due to the negativity that they already felt, they became very sensitive to other people's comments, whose levels ranged from low to high. Moreover, across the three levels, the behavioral manifestations of depression were most evident, such as being tired most of the time and having the inability or losing energy to get out of bed.

The last three tables were tables 15-17. They presented the significant relationships between stress and anxiety, stress and depression, and anxiety and depression, respectively. These results present the interconnectedness between them. The significant relationship between the three conditions, namely stress, anxiety, and depression, was also present in other literature. Adams et al.'s (2021) study on parents' stress levels, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, significantly increased. In addition to their findings, it was presented that parents who had prolonged periods of high levels of stress may also have a greater chance of

developing higher levels of anxiety and depression. This was evident in this study's results, correlating the levels of stress between the other two factors and anxiety with depression.

Conclusions

There is a significant proportion of parents who did not exhibit indications of stress, anxiety, or depression. Nevertheless, there were parents who reported experiencing varying degrees of these conditions, with manifestations evident across cognitive, emotional, behavioral, and physiological domains. Notably, certain manifestations were consistently observed across different levels of severity, suggesting that individuals could experience these symptoms regardless of the specific level of stress, anxiety, or depression they were experiencing. Moreover, it was evident that there was a significant relationship between stress and anxiety, stress and depression, and anxiety and depression.

Recommendations

Based on the results found in the study, the following are recommended:

1. Another research will be conducted to parents of which each questionnaire will be given in a separate schedule.
2. Use the result of the study in school, church, or local community in creating intervention programs for parents who may have experienced symptoms of stress, anxiety, and depression.
3. Utilize this output as a tool to educate children in understanding the mental health of the parents.
4. Use the results as a reference to understand themselves and how the variables in the study may have affected them, their family, and their activities. Thus, allowing them to potentially grasp the idea of reaching out for help should they find the need to do so.
5. The results of this study can also be used as a reference for future researchers should they conduct a similar study but in a different setting.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

All applicable institutional guidelines where the study was conducted were followed. The participants were informed of their freedom to answer the surveys. All who had submitted their answers had written informed consent.

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